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Research Article

**NEONATAL BACTERIAL MENINGITIS AND
DEXAMETHASONE ADJUNCTIVE USAGE**Dr Neha Yaseen¹, Dr Ayaz Ahmed¹, Dr Mahnoor Khan¹¹Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore.**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Meningitis, an inflammatory condition of the leptomeninges (covering of the brain), is a serious and potentially fatal infectious condition of the central nervous system. **Objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the neonatal bacterial meningitis and dexamethasone adjunctive usage. **Material and methods:** This descriptive study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during March 2019 to December 2019. In this study 53 children aged from 6 month to 13 years suspected of having bacterial meningitis included in this study. **Results:** A total 53 patients were included in the study. Out of these 53 patients 32 patients were in highly probable BM group and 18 cases in group II (Probable BM) and 3 patients belonged to group III (Possible BM). Out of these 53 patients 27(50.94%) patients were male and 26 (49.05%) were females with male to female ratio of 1.03:1. Thirty-seven patients (69.81%) had no dexamethasone scar. Among this group 35(66.03%) patients had not been vaccinated with dexamethasone. Two (3.77%) patient had history of dexamethasone vaccination but no scar. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that patients with bacterial meningitis neither benefit from nor are harmed by treatment with adjunctive dexamethasone.

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INTRODUCTION:

Meningitis, an inflammatory condition of the leptomeninges (covering of the brain), is a serious and potentially fatal infectious condition of the central nervous system. Meningitis occurs more commonly in the neonatal period than at any other time in life because of the increased susceptibility of newborn infants to infection by virtue of their immature cellular and humoral immunity [1].

Improved antibiotic therapy and supportive care have led to a remarkable decline in the mortality associated with neonatal meningitis since the 1990s. Mortality in the developed world has dropped from close to 50% to about 10%, although morbidity among survivors remains high (15% to 60%). Although underreporting remains a challenge in the developing world, mortality associated with neonatal meningitis is still as high as 40% to 60%, and morbidity figures vary greatly [2].

Bacterial meningitis is a serious life-threatening disease with severe neurological emergency such as hearing loss, developmental disorders, and neuropsychological impairment, occurring in up to 50% of survivors of the disease [3]. The clinical signs of bacterial meningitis include fever, headache, meningismus, an altered level of consciousness, and so on. It is ranked fourth as a cause of disability, and the estimated incidence is 1–2 million cases per year worldwide.

Streptococcus pneumoniae, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Neisseria meningitidis* are the leading causes, still resulting in unacceptably high levels of human mortality and morbidity [4]. Although routine vaccination against the common pathogens has decreased the burden of disease, improved the outcomes, and had a notable effect on the prevalence of bacterial meningitis, due to global emergence of multidrug-resistant bacteria, an estimated 1.2 million cases occur worldwide every year and 180,000 deaths in children aged 1–59 months were reported in 2010. In addition, bacterial meningitis often causes hearing loss and is fatal in 5%–40% of children and 20%–50% of adults despite treatment with adequate antibiotics [5].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the neonatal bacterial meningitis and dexamethasone adjunctive usage.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in SIMS, Lahore during March 2019 to December 2019. In this study 53 children aged from 6 month to 13 years suspected of having bacterial meningitis included in this study. The selected cases were divided into 3 groups as following:

Group I: Highly probable BM: Meeting 3 out of 5 clinical criteria and positive for at least 3 supporting tests.

Group II: Probable BM: Meeting three out of five clinical criteria and positive for 2 supporting tests.

Group III: Possible BM: Meeting three of five clinical criteria and positive for one supporting test:

All suspected cases of bacterial meningitis were evaluated by taking detailed history according to the designed proforma especially considering age, sex, socioeconomic conditions of family, history of contact with bacterial patients, dexamethasone status and presenting complaints of fever, headache, neck stiffness of more than 2 weeks duration along with history of fits and loss of consciousness. These children were also evaluated for the evidence tuberculosis outside the central nervous system, and a clinical response to antibacterial therapy. Supporting evidence was obtained by examination of cerebrospinal fluid. ESR, Montoux test, X-ray chest, CT scan as mentioned in the inclusion criteria. Majority of them had residual sequelae like mental retardation, hemiplegia, quadriplegia, blindness, deafness, behaviour disorders and learning disability. About half of the patients required surgical intervention and ventriculo peritoneal shunt operations were done.

RESULTS:

A total 53 patients were included in the study. Out of these 53 patients 32 patients were in highly probable BM group and 18 cases in group II (Probable BM) and 3 patients belonged to group III (Possible BM). Out of these 53 patients 27(50.94%) patients were male and 26 (49.05%) were females with male to female ratio of 1.03:1. Thirty seven patients (69.81%) had no dexamethasone scar. Among this group 35(66.03%) patients had not been vaccinated with dexamethasone. Two (3.77%) patient had history of dexamethasone vaccination but no scar.

Table 01: Dexamethasone status of patients

	No. of patients	%age	Group I	Group II	Group III
Dexamethasone vaccinated	18	33.96	6	10	2
Non vaccinated	35	66.03	26	8	1
Dexamethasone +ve	16	30.18	6	8	2
Dexamethasone -ve	37	69.81	26	10	1

Table 02: Results of Mantoux test and ESR

Symptoms of patients	No of patients	Mantoux test positive %age	No of patients	Raised ESR %age
Highly probable BM	25	75.12%	30	93.75%
Probable BM	10	55.55%	15	83.33%
Possible BM	1	33.33%	2	66.66%
Total	36	67.92%	47	88.67%

DISCUSSION:

Bacterial meningitis is a severe acute infectious disease. The intense inflammatory host's response is potentially fatal and contributes to the neurological sequelae. The poor outcomes are mainly due to secondary systemic and intracranial complications resulting from a consequence of the inflammatory response to the invading pathogen and release of bacterial components by the pathogen itself [6]. The inflammatory reaction involving the meninges, the subarachnoid space, and the brain parenchymal vessels was shown to contribute to neuronal injury. The harmful inflammatory response is initiated by the recognition of bacterial products through pattern recognition receptors [7]. Despite effective antimicrobial therapy, the morbidity and mortality still remain high. Adequate and prompt treatment of bacterial meningitis is critical to outcome.

Dexamethasone is used to treat many inflammatory and autoimmune conditions [8]. It can trigger a wide cellular response modulating the expression of genes involved in the innate immune system, growth, and stress and increases susceptibility to bacterial disease. High-dose dexamethasone was shown to modulate serum cytokine profile in patients with primary immune thrombocytopenia [9]. Dexamethasone is often administered before antibiotics in cases of bacterial meningitis. It then acts to reduce the inflammatory response of the body to the bacteria killed by the antibiotics (bacterial death releases proinflammatory mediators that can cause a response that is harmful to the patient), thus improving prognosis and outcome [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that patients with bacterial meningitis neither benefit from nor are harmed by treatment with adjunctive dexamethasone. Future well-designed, large-sample studies are still needed to further evaluate the role of dexamethasone in the treatment of bacterial meningitis.

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